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Preface: Recent trends in natural polymers, bio-composites and bio-nanocomposites

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Preface: Nature is the source of countless and priceless resources, which demand human intelligence to maximize their potential. In this context, the use of renewable resources is an increasingly relevant alternative. Renewable resources in natural polymers, biocomposites, and bionanocomposites are increasingly researched, and substantial advances have been achieved, leading academia and Industry to in-depth research in these fields.

A clear picture of the *International Conference on Natural Polymers (ICNP)* can be obtained using a simple analysis of frequency of top key words used in the titles of the abstracts. This allows us to infer that the three most used words in these titles were polymer, properties & applications. Thus, the importance of studying the relationships between polymeric materials and their properties is again proven. Besides that, we must always think about the applications of these materials, which will make our planet a more rationally explored place.

These efforts to better use our resources are much more productive when led by one of the most brilliant scientific minds of our time. The chairman of the conference, Professor Sabu Thomas and his team is an excellent example of productive capacity, combined with a sense of humanity that makes all events around them with unique growth opportunities. The last ICNP could not be different!

Again, ICNP-2019 gave us the rare opportunity to share knowledge among hundreds of researchers from different countries (India, Russia, Brazil, South Africa, France, Nepal, Malaysia, and the Czech Republic)!

Finally, I hope that this special issue will be useful for all of you!

